

EFFECTIVE & SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION BY PREFABRICATION METHOD

Jayesh Magar*¹

*¹Department of Civil Engineering, Datta Meghe College of Engineering, Airoli, Navi Mumbai, India.

ABSTRACT

The construction activity in which the building components are made offsite in a factory and then transported to the location for assembling process is Prefabrication construction. This type of construction is already been practiced in developed countries but for developing and underdeveloped countries this type of construction methodology is still unknown. Prefabrication construction is carried out in many different ways depending according on the methodology, structure, materials etc. We will be discussing about Prefabrication and dividing it based on its structure and materials used. As there are many advantages of the modern Prefabrication construction technique it also has a few drawbacks. The aim of Prefabrication technique is to built a well design house without spending much money and time. This construction technique has been proven to the best technique in saving the cost and money. In this paper we are going to discuss about how prefabrication is a effective construction technique, its application areas, its advantages and disadvantages.

KEYWORDS: Prefabrication, technique, construction, methodology, structure.

I. INTRODUCTION

Prefabrication construction technique is a process of gathering the required parts from the factory and then transporting these components or sub components to the required location. Prefabrication is most conventional construction process as compared to the traditional method. The making of required parts for construction is called as off-site construction or off- site fabrication. It involves manufacturing and building the required housing panels, walls, glass frames etc.

In the developed countries where prefabrication is taken into practice have various technology to use prefabrication method, and most of them try to focus on reducing duration, produce less waste, and costing. As compared to the traditional method, prefabrication gives us a wide range of designs to make the house look more attractive.

Most of the architects prefer Prefabrication construction as it gives them wide range of materials to use in construction, but most of them prefer light weight materials. Designers prefer wood and steel materials in construction. To do prefabrication it is very important to have a deep knowledge about the subject and also many years of on site experience.

Apart from glass and wood we can also use Glass fiber reinforced polymer(GRFP) as a material in construction. GRFP is a cost effective material and it is also resistant to corrosion and also a light weight material. However these construction methods and technologies requires deep and massive knowledge about the materials, and also its application on site which requires skilled labours.

In many countries these methods are still unknown as they are not developed or under development state. Because of this the upcoming future of the country the students are unaware of such modernization techniques and also they do not get any experience. This has caused decrease in prefabrication construction.

In many countries which experience earthquakes or floods more often do not tend to use prefabrication construction as it is more dangerous for the countries and people in that country. Where as in many developed countries have start using prefabrication and started importing its skills and techniques. In today's date prefabrication has a

important part in many developing structures and buildings. By adapting prefabrication technique, the countries development will get a boost.

The main aim of this article started with a local survey on different construction site location where even now a days old construction techniques are used. And through this article I wanted to give prefabrication construction a start to step forward towards faster development. The main work of this article is to discuss about various methods of prefabrication construction based on there materials and structures.

Concept of prefabrication construction:

In this word prefabrication, prefab itself means “made beforehand”, in which things are made in sections and then assembled. Similarly in construction the houses are also build in prefab manner and hence this technique is called as prefabrication construction. This construction technique is not some random method, not only houses, bungalows or buildings but the world famous, one of the tallest building in Dubai Burj Khalifa, was also made by using prefabrication technique. The sky city building in Changsha, China was also build by using prefabrication method. These prefab buildings and houses are made in accordance with International Building Code (IBC).

In prefabricated houses the on site work is less. It just involves assembling the parts, connecting plumbing lines and electric lines and then sealing that part. Manufactured houses are typically build on a permanent foundation, and cannot be distinguished differently if designed correctly.

These prefab homes are purchased from a construction sales company, assembled by the contract company available in locality, and necessary repairs are made to build the home. It is important to keep in mind to repair plumbing before the warranty expires or else it might cost you more than usual. It is also important to do the roof repair before rain comes or else it will lead to leakage problems.

II. METHODOLOGY

The work on this research paper started with a general survey on several construction sites who had old construction type work which lead us to find a modern way to do construction effectively and sustainably. Then prefabrication method came to our light. To get some knowledge and see if is it really proved to be effective and long lasting as compared to the traditional method I took a look at its historical background. The main purpose behind all this research was to gain some knowledge about different methods of prefabrication that are used in developed countries.

To get the main objectives gratified by this research, it is classified into two parts:

1. Literature review of related work in prefabrication and its definition, methods, techniques, systems.
2. Materials in building construction, and its advantages, disadvantages and its role in future construction process and market.

There were two categories for this research:

1. Empirical studies: To investigate appropriate prefabrication systems used for building construction.
2. Prefabrication systems assembling behavior: Recognizing relationship between prefabrication systems and its assembling process.

The paper consist of advantages and disadvantages of prefabrication construction, and from this we got to know that prefabrication is the future. To prove the point that prefabrication is the future, in Mohali, Punjab, India, a entrepreneur named Harpal Singh constructed a 10 storey building in just 48 hours in 2012. The building created a history in the construction field. No bricks and sand were used in the construction of this building the outside walls of the building contained PUF panels (polyurethane panels). No compromise was made in the quality materials used in the building. Over 200 skilled engineers and workers were appointed for this project who worked day and night.

Prefabricated structural systems:

Prefabricated structural systems are divided into several types depending upon the methodology of construction, type of materials used in building, type of structure built, types of designs of building etc. According to this work the prefabrication construction is displayed based on structural configuration. The various possible structures of prefabrication are explained in detail below.

Using the framework in building saves a lot of money and time in construction.

Method of prefabrication construction:

Panelized wood framing:

Measured fragments of laminated timber are transformed into solid frames, which later with the help of plywood, are transformed into panels. These frames cover all the area as they are 72 feet long, and they also act as excellent roofing panels. Constructing these roofing panels saves a lot of time and apart from that it also provides safety to the house. The main advantage of wood framing is it provides extra space, excellent and acoustic insulation.

Fig-1: Panelized wood framing

Timber framing

Timber framing is very popular construction technique as timber houses are always in demand as it provides more convenience than other homes. The timber frame itself is so well protected that it does not allow any wet or dry rot to appear on the frame. Timber framing is so sustainable as it produces less waste. If local timber is used it requires low embodied energy. A prefabricated timber frame is usually erected faster when on site as compared to brick and block work. The designers also can give any design they feel without any hesitation. Also we can achieve higher quality if we do off site fabrication.

Fig-2: Timber Framing

Concrete System

Concrete frame is a type of concrete which is prepared at first, casted and then cured off-site, mostly in a factory environment with the help of moulds. Then these precast concrete frames are joined to each others to make a complete structure. It is basically used for the construction of components like columns, beams, floors, wall panels, tunnels pipes etc. It improves the durability and also improves aesthetics of the components.

Fig-3: Prefabricated Concrete Building

Steel Framing

Using steel frames are very beneficial when it comes to customization, speed of construction, and decreased maintenance and insurance cost. The main advantage of steel buildings is it can last for decades, remains useful for entire life. Steel structures can withstand high winds, earthquakes, and other events. It always remains the go-to material and also very trusted by all companies as steel is very durable and has high strength. The main advantage is the steel is 100 percent eco friendly and also can be recycled and reused. Also it saves enough time.

Fig-4: Prefabricated steel house

Standardization and Customization

Both the terminologies are of very importance in the prefab construction. Standardization and customization holds a very important place in prefab construction. Standardization means a standard set up by a system to measure the quality, quantity, weight etc. In short standardization is a sort of expectation which the person is supposed to fulfill. Standardization is set up by bringing various associations like customers, regulators manufacturers to discuss about the materials, services. Customization is actually inverse of standardization. Customization enables the customers to customize and personalized there house according to there expectations to meet there needs. Customization not only reduces the cost but also minimize the duration in making the house. Many benefits are seen in both product and process of standardization. In 2001, research scholars Alistair Gibb and Frank Isack stated that standardization has a great impact on reducing the cost. Standardization processes allows the project associates to acknowledge what is needed, from whom and by when.

Fig-5: Prefabricated panel

Modular Vs. Traditional Construction

If we compare modular and traditional way of construction then there is a huge marginal difference. Modular construction is way more effective in terms of time, cost, sustainability, site waste, structural integrity. The main thing is the wastage of water on site. While my visit to a construction site, I noticed a huge amount wastage of water for curing process. A wall needs a curing of 14 days, means 14 days regular water supply to just one wall and where are so many no of walls means a lot of liters of water is wasted. And not just water wastage of many things happen on site which no one notices. In accordance to that modular construction is way better in saving water and many resources and much more effective and sustainable. Also after making a wall or a slab or column it requires a certain amount of settling time which in a aspect is a waste of time. Also the traditional construction lot of time , during which rainy season comes which again leads to closing of site because of heavy rainfall and many difficulties arise like transport delays etc on other site in modular construction does not has any such kind of difficulties and is much more effective and sustainable. Funding is also a main aspect in construction, traditional construction requires a smooth flow of money, in case if the cast flow is stopped it leads to a blockage in construction and the site work is stopped. Where as in modular construction it just requires a one time investment and in that particular amount the structure is made in less time. So as a result in all aspect modular construction is more beneficial than traditional.

Advantages:

➤ Durability

Durability of prefab houses is very much better than traditional houses. The modern houses are made by modern equipment which gives more protection to the walls from damaging. Modular houses are build with superior quality materials which takes care of the environment and makes the house more durable.

➤ Less Mess

Since the product is pre-manufactured in the factory, there is no need to cover machinery or adjacent offices from dust and noise when erecting.

➤ Fast Installations

A typical 12' x 16' building is installed in less than a day. Hence quicker occupancy is achieved.

➤ Expandability

With the fast paced growth of today's business, change is inevitable. This system gives the flexibility to adapt and accommodate. Modular construction lets you upsize or downsize with minimal down time.

➤ **Sound Quality**

As compared to the traditional construction, modular prefabrication construction has more sound insulating value. Modular construction has almost zero sound attenuation value.

➤ **Reusable**

With the use of prefabrication construction you can easily relocate the house from one place to another as it is, or you can dismantle the components, transport them and assemble them as they were with the help of local contractors.

➤ **Cost Savings**

Prefabricated buildings have lower initial cost and faster delivery as compared to conventional buildings, especially when it comes to low rise buildings. Prefabrication modular construction on an average saves upto 20 to 30 percent of the cost which is actually beneficial.

➤ **Tax Benefits**

The depreciation period for modular houses is 7 years as compared to conventional construction which is 39 and half years. As we can accelerate the construction we can also regain the money faster and hence save the money.

➤ **Time Saving**

No need to schedule and manage dozens of subcontractors going in and out of your facility with little or no accountability. Our staff can take care of all your needs.

Disadvantages:

- The components might break while transporting so extra care has to be taken while transporting .
- Skilled labours who have on site experience are required for this work for connecting the precast units.
- Each member component should be of accurate size and strength or else it may cause unbalancing of structure.
- There is a lot of paper work involved for getting prefabricated structure approved and soil testing and land surveying also needs to be done accurately.
- Selling a prefab house is a big problem as the people do not prefer to buy the prefab houses thinking it is of cheap quality.
- The land you are purchasing should be suitable for prefabrication construction or else it will lead to waste of money.

III. CONCLUSION

Comparing the overall aspects prefabrication modular system is better option in today's world. It will give birth to a new industries too for prefab construction giving many people employment. The main reason which makes prefab houses more attractive is the cost. Many people do not buy houses because of its high cost but prefab houses are very cheaper for the poor and middle class people and much more affordable. Prefabrication is called the future of the world as it improves the economy of that nation. Today prefabrication construction is not just a development plan of action but it has also entered into the colossal market. Now a days the entrepreneurs and business person are also funding and encouraging to built prefabricated houses as they are more affordable and attracted by many people by its advantages. Because of its remarkable characteristics prefabrication system can be the future of the upcoming construction world.

IV. REFERENCES

- [1] Limthongtang, R. "Comparison between prefabrication construction and normal construction" Thesis, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand, 2005.

- [2] Fetters, T. "The Lustron home. Jefferson", N.C.: McFarland, 2002.
- [3] Best, R., and De Valence, G. "Design and construction: Building in value. Routledge". USA, 2002.
- [4] Harris, F., McCaffer, R. "Modern Construction Management", Blackwell Science, 5th Edition, London, 2001.
- [5] Koskela, L., Howell, G., Ballard, G., and Tommelein, I. "The Foundations of Lean Construction." Elsevier, Oxford, UK, 2002.
- [6] Applied Technology Council, Seismic Evaluation and Retrofit of Concrete Buildings. Vol. 1, Report No. SSC 96-01, 1996.
- [7] Baghchesaraei, A and Baghchesaraei, O.R. "Essential words for Architects and Structural Engineers", Naghoos Publication. Tehran, 2014.
- [8] Best, R., and De Valence, G. (2002). Design and construction: Building in value. Routledge. USA.
- [9] Kim, T. "Comparison of prefab homes and a sitebuilt home: Quantitative evaluation of four different types of prefab homes and a site-built home", Southern California University. USA, 2009.
- [10] Tam, M. "Impact on structure of labour market resulting from large-scale implementation of prefabrication" Advanced in Building Technology. Vol. 1. Hong Kong, 2002.